

Adenosine receptors. Part 2 : 4-Substituted amino-7- β -(D-ribofuranosyl)-pyrrolo[3,2-*d*]pyrimidine derivatives as possible adenosine receptor agonists[†]

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Abstract : Adenosine is known to exert a wide range of pharmacological effects. This effect of adenosine suggested that modified analogues of adenosine might provide therapeutically useful active agents. Thus, in this paper, a series of novel N⁶-substituted-9-deaza adenosine or N⁴-substituted pyrrolo[3,2-*d*]pyrimidines with ribose moiety were prepared in 14 steps.

Keywords : N⁴-Substituted pyrrolo[3,2-*d*]pyrimidine derivatives, 6-substituted adenosine derivatives with ribose moiety, adenosine receptors, adenosine receptor agonists.

Introduction

Extracellular purines [e.g. adenosine, adenosine 5'-diphosphate (ADP) and adenosine 5'-triphosphate (ATP)] and pyrimidines [e.g. uridine 5'-diphosphate (UDP) and uridine 5'-triphosphate (UTP)] are important signaling molecules that mediate diverse biological effects via cell-surface receptors termed purinergic receptors. These receptors were first formally recognized by Burnstock in 1978¹. He proposed that these receptors can be divided into two classes termed 'P1-purinoreceptors', recognizing adenosine (1) as principal natural ligand, and 'P2-purinoreceptors', which are activated by ATP and ADP. In addition, receptors for pyrimidines are included within the P2 receptor family². The P1 and P2 receptor families are both further subdivided according to convergent molecular, biochemical, and pharmacological evidence. The P1 receptors or adenosine receptors consist of 4 subtypes classified as A₁, A_{2A}, A_{2B} and A₃. Adenosine is a nucleoside that consists of a sugar part, D-ribofuranose, which is linked to the purine base adenine via a β -glycosidic bond. Adenosine is metabolically and structurally related to the bioactive nucleotides, adenosine 5'-monophosphate

(AMP), ADP, ATP, and cyclic adenosine monophosphate (cAMP).

G protein-coupled receptors (GPCRs) constitute a large family of heptahelical, integral membrane proteins that mediate a wide variety of physiological processes, ranging from the transmission of light and odorant signals to the mediation of neurotransmission and hormonal action³. The ARs are G protein-coupled receptors (GPCRs) and consist of a single polypeptide chain that transverses the membrane from the extracellular side beginning at the N terminus to form seven transmembrane helices (TMs). The A₁ and A₃ receptors preferentially couple to G_i protein to inhibit adenylate cyclase and consequently the production of cyclic AMP (cAMP) and the A_{2A} and A_{2B} subtypes stimulate the production of cAMP by coupling to G_s or G_o.

Synthetic adenosine agonists are under development as therapeutic agents. The half-life of adenosine in circulation is very short (~1 s), due to the action of enzymes that convert it to inosine (adenosine deaminase) or phosphorylate it to 5'-AMP (adenosine kinase), or due to its uptake through nucleoside transporters (such as the

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equilibrative transporter ENT1)⁴⁻⁶. Therefore, analogues of adenosine for selective activation of ARs tend to prevent these processes and thereby lengthen the half-life. For example, the A₃-selective agonist IB-MECA has a half-life of 8–9 h in man⁷. Adenosine itself is in use as an AR agonist for the treatment of paroxysmal supraventricular tachycardia (through the A₁ receptor) and in radionuclide myocardial perfusion imaging (through the A_{2A} receptor). For those applications, the short half-life of adenosine is advantageous. There are many selective and potent synthetic AR agonists that have been introduced as research tools and for consideration to be used in humans.

Some of the selected A₁ adenosine receptor agonists include cyclopentyl adenosine (CPA, **2**), 2-chloro-N⁶-cyclopentyl adenosine (CCPA, **3**), (2*S*)-N⁶-[2-endo-norbornyl]adenosine [S(-)ENBA, **4**], *N*-[(1*S*,2*S*)-2-hydroxycyclopentyl]adenosine (GR79236, **5**), *N*-[(3*R*)-tetrahydro-3-furanyl]adenosine (CVT-510, Tecadenoson, **6**) are only N⁶-substituted adenosine⁸⁻¹¹.

Since there are no reports on C-nucleosides, we planned to synthesize some N⁶-substituted 9-deazaadenosine with ribose moiety.

Biological activity of these molecules is under investigation and will be reported later.

Results and discussion

Chemistry :

The nomenclature of adenosine moiety and 9-deaza adenosine (i.e pyrrolo[3,2-*d*]pyrimidine) are different; here N⁶-position of adenosine moiety corresponds to N⁴-position.

N⁶-Alkyl/aryl amino adenosines **2a-f** were prepared from commercially available D-ribose (**7**) in 14 steps (Scheme 1). Compound **8** was prepared with high yield from **7** by treating with MeOH and H₂SO₄. The protection of three hydroxyl groups of **8** using BnCl and NaH (60%) in DMF as solvent resulted into compound **9**. Further, demethylation of **9** using 4 *N* HCl (aq.) and 1,4-dioxane resulted into the formation of **10**. Treatment of compound **10** with sodium hydride (60%) and diethyl cyanomethylphosphonate provided **11**^{15,19,20}. Reaction of cyanomethyl derivative (**11**) with Brederick's reagent [*tert*-butoxy bis(dimethylamino)methane] gave compound **12**^{14,15,20}. The hydrolysis of dimethylamino group of compound (**12**) was successfully achieved with trifluoroacetic acid in water and chloroform without affecting other groups in the molecule and the resultant compound **13** was isolated^{14,15,17,20}. The reaction of compound **13** with ethyl glycinate hydrochloride in the presence of sodium acetate in methanol provided compound **14**^{14,16}. The protection

1 : Adenosine

2 : CPA, R = H
3 : CCPA, R = Cl

4 : S(-)ENBA

5 : GR79236

6 : CVT-510 (Tecadenoson)

of the amino group of the compound **14** was done with ethyl chloroformate in the presence of a base which was necessary for the next step of cyclization^{14,16}. The compound **15** was obtained through cyclization *in situ* with DBN followed by deprotection of carbamate with sodium carbonate resulting into a mixture of alpha and beta isomers (**16**)^{14,16}. This mixture was purified by column chromatography on silica gel to provide both separate isomers **17** (alpha) and **18** (beta)^{14,18}. The stereo-chemistry was assigned by NMR based upon the literature reports. The desired beta isomer **18** was further taken for reaction with formamidine acetate in *n*-BuOH, which gave compound **19**^{12-14,19}. Chlorination of **19** using POCl₃ under buffer conditions afforded compound **20**¹⁴. The final target molecules **22a-f** were prepared by reaction of **20** with different amines using triethylamine as base in *n*-butanol followed by deprotection of benzyl groups in **21a-f** by using BCl₃ (1 M in DCM)¹⁹.

Experimental

General procedures :

All solvents and chemicals were used as purchased without further purification. The progress of all reactions was monitored on Merck precoated silica gel plates (with fluorescence indicator UV254). Column chromatography was performed with silica gel 60 (230–400 mesh size) with the solvent mixtures specified in the corresponding experiment. Spots were visualized by irradiation with ultraviolet light (254 nm). Melting points (m.p.) were taken in open capillaries on a Stuart melting point apparatus using Veego VMP-D and are uncorrected. Proton ¹H NMR spectra recorded on model BRUKER ADVANCE DPX 300 using DMSO-*d*₆ as solvent. Mass spectra recorded on model AGILENT G1946 (1100 Series). The purity of compounds was checked by HPLC on model AGILENT 1260 series at wave length 260 nm and the column used was LichroCART 125-4 HPLC Cartridge, Purospher RP-18 (5 μm).

Preparation of 2-hydroxymethyl-5-methoxy-tetrahydrofuran-3,4-diol (**8**) :

To a solution of D-ribose (**7**, 50.0 g, 333.04 mmol) in methanol (800 mL) was added conc. sulfuric acid (5 mL, 93.80 mmol) and stirred at 0–5 °C for 16 h. The reaction mixture was neutralized using triethylamine (32.74 mL, 234.89 mmol), concentrated to dryness and co-distilled twice with 100 mL toluene to remove trace amount of

water to furnish *O*-methyl-D-ribofuranose (46 g, 84.17%) as a pale yellow oily mass.

¹H NMR (300 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆) : δ 5.55–5.42 (3H, bs), 5.11 (1H, d, *J* 10.8 Hz), 3.97 (1H, dd, *J* 12.5 and 11.8 Hz), 3.90 (1H, d, *J* 9.9 Hz), 3.51 (1H, dd, *J* 10.6 and 8.4 Hz), 3.42 (2H, m), 3.22 (3H, s); MS (ES⁺) 165.3 (M+1), (ES⁻) 163.3 (M-1).

Preparation of 3,4-bis-benzyloxy-2-benzyloxymethyl-5-methoxytetrahydrofuran (**9**) :

To a clean dry RBF, DMF (625 mL) was charged and sodium hydride (47.8 g, 60% in mineral oil, 1195.0 mmol) was added under nitrogen atmosphere and the reactants were cooled to 0–5 °C. Benzyl chloride (192 g, 1516.8 mmol) was added slowly over a period of 30 min maintaining the temperature below 5 °C. Cooling was removed and the mixture was stirred for 1 h below 20 °C. Again it was cooled to 5 °C and a solution of *O*-methyl-D-ribofuranose (**8**, 50.0 g, 304.6 mmol) in DMF (200 mL) was added between 5–10 °C over a period of 1 h 20 min. After addition was complete, the reaction mixture was left overnight at RT. Reaction mass was quenched by adding ice-water (500 mL) and extracted with toluene (3 × 350 mL). The combined organic layers were washed with brine (1 L) and dried over Na₂SO₄ (100 g). The solvent was concentrated to dryness to give crude (210 g) as brown oily mass, which was taken as such for next step.

¹H NMR (300 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆) : δ 7.40–7.11 (15H, m), 5.90 (1H, s), 4.65–4.43 (6H, m), 4.12–4.07 (1H, m), 3.97 (1H, dd, *J* 9.8 and 10.4 Hz), 3.90 (1H, d, *J* 12.2 Hz), 3.55 (1H, dd, *J* 14.4 and 11.4 Hz), 3.42 (1H, dd, *J* 3.6 and 5.7 Hz), 3.22 (3H, s); MS (ES⁺) 435.51 (M+1), (ES⁻) 433.53 (M-1).

Preparation of 3,4-bis-benzyloxy-5-benzyloxymethyl-tetrahydrofuran-2-ol (**10**) :

To a solution of crude 3,4-bis-benzyloxy-2-benzyloxymethyl-5-methoxytetrahydrofuran (**9**, 100 g, 230.1 mmol) in 1,4-dioxane (378 mL) was added aqueous 4 N HCl (133 mL, 532 mmol). The mixture was heated at reflux for 4 h. The reaction mixture was allowed to attain room temperature and extracted with ethyl acetate (1 L, 500 mL and 250 mL). The combined organic layers were washed with saturated aqueous NaHCO₃ (1 L), brine (1 L) and dried over sodium sulfate (100 g) and filtered. The filtrate was concentrated under vacuum

Scheme 1. Synthesis of compounds **22a-f**.

Reagents and conditions : (i) MeOH, H₂SO₄; (ii) BnCl, NaH (60%), DMF; (iii) 4 N HCl, 1,4-dioxane; (iv) diethyl cyanomethylphosphonate, NaH (60%), 1,2-dimethoxy ethane; (v) Bredereck's reagent, DMF, RT; (vi) TFA, water, chloroform, RT; (vii) ethyl glycinate.HCl, CH₃COONa, MeOH, RT; (viii) ethyl chloroformate, DBN, dichloromethane, 0 °C; (ix) DBN, RT; (x) Na₂CO₃, MeOH, RT; (xi) formamidine acetate, *n*-BuOH, 120 °C; (xii) POCl₃, benzyl triethyl ammoniumchloride, *N,N*-dimethyl aniline, CH₃CN, 80 °C; (xiii) primary or secondary amine, triethylamine, *n*-BuOH, 120 °C; (xiv) BCl₃ (1 M in DCM), DCM.

to furnish crude product which was purified by flash chromatography over silica gel eluting with ethyl acetate in *n*-hexane (10 to 50%) to furnish desire product (60 g, 62.0%), a mixture of isomers as an oil.

¹H NMR (300 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆) : δ 7.37–7.28 (15H,

m), 6.58 (1H, d, *J* 6.6 Hz), 5.82 (0.3H, d, *J* 8.4 Hz), 5.26 (0.3H, m), 5.21 (0.7H, m), 4.65–4.43 (6H, m), 4.12 (0.3H, m), 4.06–3.97 (1.3H, m), 3.92–3.88 (0.7H, m), 3.80 (0.7H, m), 3.58–3.41 (2H, m); MS (ES⁺) 421.51 (M+1), (ES⁻) 419.53 (M-1).

Table 1. Physico-chemical properties of novel N⁶-substituted adenosines

Sr. no.	Compd.	Amines used (NR ₁ R ₂)	Molecular formula	Molecular weight	M.p. (°C)
1.	22a		C ₁₇ H ₂₄ N ₄ O ₄	348.40	155–159
2.	22b		C ₁₆ H ₂₂ N ₄ O ₄	334.37	164–167
3.	22c		C ₁₆ H ₂₂ N ₄ O ₄	334.37	167–169
4.	22d		C ₁₅ H ₂₀ N ₄ O ₄	320.34	172–174
5.	22e		C ₁₅ H ₂₀ N ₄ O ₄	320.34	184–186
6.	22f		C ₁₄ H ₁₈ N ₄ O ₄	306.32	166–169

Preparation of 2-(3,4-bis(benzyloxy)-5-(benzyloxymethyl)-tetrahydrofuran-2-yl)-acetonitrile (11) :

To a stirred solution of NaH (60%, 7.13 g, 178.35 mmol) in monoglyme (153 mL) was added ethyl cyanomethylphosphonate (31.6 g, 178.38 mmol) at 0 ± 5 °C over a period of 2 h. The resulting mixture was stirred for 2 h at 0 °C and a solution of 3,4-bis-benzyloxy-5-benzyloxymethyltetrahydrofuran-2-ol (**10**, 60.0 g, 142.68 mmol) in monoglyme (65 mL) was added to it at 0 ± 5 °C over a period of 2 h. The resulting mixture was stirred for 15 h at RT. The reaction mixture was slowly quenched with water (500 mL) and extracted with EtOAc (2 × 250 mL). The combined organic extracts were washed with brine, dried over Na₂SO₄, filtered and concentrated under reduced pressure to give the crude product (78 g) as a brown oily mass. This was purified by flash column chromatography (silica gel, eluting with 0–30% ethyl acetate in *n*-hexane) to afford (3,4-bis-benzyloxy-5-benzyloxymethyltetrahydrofuran-2-yl)acetonitrile (48 g, 75.90%), a mixture of isomer as an oil. MS (ES⁺) 444.33 (M+1).

Preparation of 2-(3,4-bis-benzyloxy-5-benzyloxymethyltetrahydrofuran-2-yl)-3-dimethylaminoacrylonitrile (12) :

To a stirred a solution of (3,4-bis-benzyloxy-5-benzyloxymethyltetrahydrofuran-2-yl)acetonitrile (**11**, 34.0

g, 76.65 mmol) in DMF (480 mL) was added *tert*-butoxy-bis(dimethylamino)methane (76.64 g, 439.7 mmol) at RT. The resulting mixture was stirred for 45 h at RT. The reaction mixture was slowly quenched with water (775 mL) and extracted with EtOAc (2250 mL). The organic extracts were washed with water (775 mL), dried over Na₂SO₄, filtered and concentrated under reduced pressure to give the crude product (34.4 g) as a brown oily mass. This was purified by flash column chromatography (silica gel, eluting with 5–40% ethyl acetate in *n*-hexane) to afford 2-(3,4-bis-benzyloxy-5-benzyloxymethyltetrahydrofuran-2-yl)-3-dimethylaminoacrylonitrile (23.29 g, 60.94%) as a brownish oily mass.

¹H NMR (300 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆) : δ 7.40–7.11 (15H, m), 6.59 (1H, s), 5.90 (1H, s), 4.65–4.43 (1H, m), 4.12–4.07 (1H, m), 3.97 (1H, dd, *J* 10.8 and 9.6 Hz), 3.90 (2H, d, *J* 6.9 Hz), 2.55 (6H, s); MS (ES⁺) 499.51 (M+1), (ES⁻) 497.53 (M-1).

Preparation of 2-(3,4-bis-benzyloxy-5-benzyloxymethyltetrahydrofuran-2-yl)-3-hydroxyacrylonitrile (13) :

To a stirred a solution of 2-(3,4-bis-benzyloxy-5-benzyloxymethyltetrahydrofuran-2-yl)-3-dimethylaminoacrylonitrile (**12**, 5.7 g, 11.43 mmol) in chloroform (104 mL) and water (57 mL) was added trifluoroacetic acid (2.17 g, 19.09 mmol) at RT. The resulting mixture was stirred for 15 h at RT. The organic layer was separated and the aqueous layer was extracted with chloroform (2 × 100 mL). The combined organic extracts were washed with water (100 mL), dried over Na₂SO₄, filtered and concentrated under reduced pressure to give product (6.42 g) as a light yellow oily mass. This was purified by flash column chromatography (silica gel, eluting with 5–40% ethyl acetate in *n*-hexane) to afford 2-(3,4-bis-benzyloxy-5-benzyloxymethyltetrahydrofuran-2-yl)-3-dimethylaminoacrylonitrile (5.1 g, 60.9%) as a brownish oily mass.

¹H NMR (300 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆) : δ 7.40–7.11 (15H, m), 5.93 (1H, s), 4.65–4.43 (1H, m), 4.12–4.07 (1H, m), 3.97 (1H, m), 3.90 (2H, d, *J* 8.1 Hz), 3.86 (1H, m); MS (ES⁺) 472.51 (M+1), (ES⁻) 470.33 (M-1).

Preparation of [2-(3,4-bis-benzyloxy-5-benzyloxymethyltetrahydrofuran-2-yl)-2-cyanovinylamino]acetic acid ethyl ester (14) :

To a stirred solution of 2-(3,4-bis-benzyloxy-5-

benzyloxymethyltetrahydrofuran-2-yl)-3-hydroxyacrylonitrile (**13**, 3.72 g, 7.89 mmol) in MeOH (46.5 mL) was added sodium acetate (1.29 g, 15.73 mmol) and ethyl glycinate.HCl (2.20 g, 15.77 mmol) at RT and then water (11.6 mL) was added to it. The resulting mixture was stirred for 12 h at RT. The reaction mixture was slowly quenched with water (378 mL) and extracted with chloroform (189 mL). The organic layer was separated and the aqueous layer was again extracted with chloroform (100 mL). The combined organic extracts were washed with water (100 mL), dried over Na₂SO₄, filtered and concentrated under reduced pressure to give product (4.25 g) as a dark brownish oily mass containing 2 spots. It was taken as such for the next step. MS (ES⁺) 557.51 (M+1), (ES⁻) 555.33 (M-1).

Preparation of 3-amino-4-(3,4-bis-benzyloxy-5-benzyloxymethyltetrahydrofuran-2-yl)-pyrrole-1,2-dicarboxylic acid diethyl ester (15) :

To a stirred solution of ethyl-[2-(3,4-bis-benzyloxy-5-benzyloxymethyltetrahydrofuran-2-yl)-2-cyanovinyl-amino]acetate (**14**, 4.25 g, 7.63 mmol) in DCM (44.43 mL) was added 1,5-diazabicyclo[4.3.0]non-5-ene (DBN) (2.84 g, 22.87 mmol) at 0 °C. A solution of ethyl chloroformate (1.24 g, 11.42 mmol) in DCM (4.44 mL) was added slowly at 0 °C to the reaction mixture and the resulting mixture was stirred for 1 h at 0 °C. TLC showed completion of reaction. The reaction mixture was further treated with ethyl chloroformate (0.231 g, 2.12 mmol) and 1,5-diazabicyclo[4.3.0]non-5-ene (DBN) (1.22 g, 9.82 mmol) and stirred for 20 h at RT. The mixture was concentrated under reduced pressure to give the crude product (10.45 g) as a brown oily mass, which was used as such for the next step. MS (ES⁺) 629.30 (M+1), (ES⁻) 627.33 (M-1).

Preparation of 3-amino-4-(3,4-bis-benzyloxy-5-benzyloxymethyltetrahydrofuran-2-yl)-1H-pyrrole-2-carboxylic acid ethyl ester (17 and 18) :

To a stirred solution of 3-amino-4-(3,4-bis-benzyloxy-5-benzyloxymethyltetrahydrofuran-2-yl)-pyrrole-1,2-dicarboxylic acid diethyl ester (**15**, 10.45 g, 16.62 mmol) in MeOH (348.25 mL) was added sodium carbonate (4.4 g, 41.55 mmol) at RT. The resulting mixture was stirred for 48 h at RT. The reaction mixture was slowly quenched with water (250 mL) and extracted with chloroform (2 ×

250 mL). The combined organic extracts were washed with water (100 mL), dried over Na₂SO₄, filtered and concentrated under reduced pressure to give crude product (6.44 g) as a mixture of two anomeric isomers (**16**) which was purified by flash chromatography on silica gel eluting with EtOAc in *n*-hexane (10–35%) to furnish 5.5 g of β isomer (**18**) and 2.35 of α isomer (**17**).

Compound **18** (β isomer) : ¹H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 8.08 (1H, s), 7.33–7.17 (15H, m), 6.64 (1H, s), 4.94–4.91 (1H, d, *J* 7.8 Hz), 4.81 (1H, d, *J* 7.8 Hz), 4.70 (1H, d, *J* 12 Hz), 4.68–4.45 (3H, m), 4.18–4.10 (2H, m), 2.06 (2H, q), 1.37 (3H, t, *J* 7.2 Hz); MS (ES⁺) 557.4 (M+1), (ES⁻) 555.3 (M-1).

Compound **17** (α isomer) : ¹H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 7.98 (1H, s), 7.25–7.19 (15H, m), 6.52 (1H, s), 4.78–4.76 (1H, d, *J* 6.6 Hz), 4.77 (1H, m), 4.70 (1H, m), 4.58–4.55 (3H, m), 4.19–4.11 (2H, m), 2.02 (2H, q), 1.33 (3H, t, *J* 7.2 Hz); MS (ES⁺) 557.4 (M+1), (ES⁻) 555.3 (M-1).

Preparation of 7-(3,4-bis-benzyloxy-5-benzyloxymethyltetrahydrofuran-2-yl)-3,5-dihydropyrrolo[3,2-d]pyrimidin-4-one (19) :

To a stirred solution of 3-amino-4-(3,4-bis-benzyloxy-5-benzyloxymethyltetrahydrofuran-2-yl)-1H-pyrrole-2-carboxylic acid ethyl ester (**18**, 15.8 g, 28.38 mmol) in *n*-butanol (347.6 mL) was added formamidine acetate (73.62 g, 709.6 mmol) at room temperature and the resulting mixture was refluxed for 12 h. The reaction mixture was cooled and the solid material was removed by filtration. The residue was partitioned between chloroform (200 mL) and water (200 mL). The organic layer was separated and the aqueous layer was further extracted with chloroform (200 mL). The combined organic layers were washed with brine (150 mL) and dried over Na₂SO₄. The solvent was concentrated to dryness under vacuum and triturated with *n*-hexane (75 mL) and filtered to give desire compound (**19**, 12.95 g, 84.49%) as an off-white solid.

¹H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 12.2 (1H, s), 10.88 (1H, s, D₂O exchangeable), 8.18 (1H, s), 7.61–7.09 (15H, m), 5.49 (1H, d, *J* 9 Hz), 4.50 (2H, s), 4.50–4.35 (4H, m), 4.26 (1H, t, *J* 12 Hz), 4.19–4.05 (2H, m), 3.63–3.50 (2H, m); MS (ES⁺) 538.4 (M+1), (ES⁻) 536.4 (M-1).

Preparation of 4-chloro-7-β-(2',3',5'-tri-O-benzyl-D-ribofuranosyl)-pyrrolo[3,2-d]pyrimidine (20) :

To a stirred solution (7-β-(2',3',5'-tri-O-benzyl-D-ribofuranosyl)-pyrrolo[3,2-d]pyrimidin-4(3H)-one (**19**, 12.5 g, 23.25 mmol), benzyltriethyl ammonium chloride (10.59 g, 46.49 mmol), *N,N*-dimethylaniline (4.23 g, 34.87 mmol) in acetonitrile (100 mL) was added phosphorous oxychloride (21.39 g, 139.50 mmol) at 80 °C and further stirred for 3 h at 80 °C. The reaction mixture was concentrated to dryness, dissolved in chloroform (250 mL) and quenched with water (250 mL). The organic layer was separated and aqueous layer was further extracted with chloroform (2 × 125 mL). The combined chloroform extracts were washed with water (250 mL), saturated sodium bicarbonate (100 mL), brine (250 mL) and dried over sodium sulphate. After filtration, the filtrate was concentrated and the residue was purified by flash chromatography on silica gel eluting with EtOAc in *n*-hexane (15%, 25%, 35%, 50%) to afford 8.9 g (68.59%) of desired product as thick oily mass.

¹H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 12.4 (1H, s), 9.35 (1H, s), 8.70 (1H, s), 7.61–6.95 (15H, m), 5.42 (1H, d, *J* 4.2 Hz), 4.52–4.40 (7H, m), 4.24–4.11 (2H, m); MS (ES⁺) 557.4 (M+1), (ES⁻) 555.4 (M-1).

General method for preparation of compounds 21a-f :

A solution of 4-chloro-7-β-(2',3',5'-tri-O-benzyl-D-ribofuranosyl)-pyrrolo[3,2-d]pyrimidine (**20**, 250 mg, 0.45 mmol), the corresponding primary or secondary amine (2.25 mmol) and triethylamine (9 mmol) in ethanol (10 mL) was heated at 80 °C for overnight. The reaction mass was concentrated to dryness to give a dark brown oily mass. Resulting crude was purified by flash chromatography (silica gel 230–400 mesh, eluent : 15–70% EtOAc in *n*-hexane) to furnish the title compound (55–78%) as syrupy mass.

General method for preparation of compounds 22a-f :

To a stirred solution of 4-substituted amino-7-β-(2',3',5'-tri-O-benzyl-D-ribofuranosyl)-pyrrolo[3,2-d]pyrimidine (**21a-f**, 0.5 g) in methylene chloride (38.75 mL) was added boron trichloride (8.04 mmol, 1 M solution in methylene chloride) at -70 °C and stirred for 1 h at same temperature. Then the reaction was brought to -30 °C over a period of 30 min, and quenched by adding a mixture of methanol : chloroform (2 : 1, 10 mL). After

the reaction mixture reached to room temperature, it was neutralized with aqueous NH₃ in methanol (10%, 10 mL) and concentrated to dryness and the residue was purified by flash chromatography on silica gel eluting with CMA : 80 (chloroform-80 : methanol-18 : NH₄OH-2) in chloroform (10%, 25%, 50% and 75%) which gave desired 4-substituted amino-7-β-(D-ribofuranosyl)-pyrrolo[3,2-d]pyrimidines (**22a-f**) (50.0 to 63.72%) as light brown to off-white solid.

4-(Cyclohexylamino)-7-β-(D-ribofuranosyl)pyrrolo[3,2-d]pyrimidine (22a) :

¹H NMR (300 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆) : δ 14.88 (1H, s), 9.86 (1H, s), 8.79 (1H, s), 8.09–8.05 (1H, d, *J* 3 Hz, D₂O exchangeable), 5.64–5.25 (3H, bs, D₂O exchangeable), 4.80–4.77 (1H, d, *J* 8.4 Hz), 4.71–4.69 (1H, m), 4.43–4.38 (1H, dd, *J* 4.8 and 5.1 Hz), 4.15–4.12 (1H, dd, *J* 6.3 and 6.9 Hz), 3.74–3.71 (2H, d, *J* 9 Hz), 3.48–3.45 (1H, m), 2.01–1.97 (4H, m), 1.69–1.65 (6H, m); MS (ES⁺) 349.3 (M+1), (ES⁻) 347.3 (M-1), HPLC purity : 98.92%.

4-(Cyclopentylamino)-7-β-(D-ribofuranosyl)pyrrolo[3,2-d]pyrimidine (22b) :

¹H NMR (300 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆) : δ 13.25 (1H, s), 9.85 (1H, s), 8.66 (1H, s), 8.04–8.03 (1H, d, *J* 9 Hz, D₂O exchangeable), 5.79–4.89 (3H, bs, D₂O exchangeable), 4.80–4.77 (1H, m), 4.61–4.59 (1H, m), 4.43–4.38 (1H, m), 4.13–4.06 (1H, dd, *J* 8.4 and 9 Hz), 3.74–3.72 (2H, d, *J* 9.6 Hz), 3.51–3.48 (1H, m), 2.08–1.99 (4H, m), 1.72–1.59 (4H, m); MS (ES⁺) 335.3 (M+1), (ES⁻) 333.3 (M-1), HPLC purity : 97.85%.

4-(Piperidino)-7-β-(D-ribofuranosyl)pyrrolo[3,2-d]pyrimidine (22c) :

¹H NMR (300 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆) : δ 11.27 (1H, s), 7.95 (1H, s), 7.28 (1H, s), 5.63–4.85 (3H, bs, D₂O exchangeable), 4.60–4.38 (1H, d, *J* 12 Hz), 4.30–4.28 (1H, dd, *J* 9.9 and 10.5 Hz), 4.22–3.98 (1H, m), 3.66–3.64 (2H, d, *J* 6 Hz), 3.50–3.46 (1H, dd, *J* 6.6 and 6.9 Hz), 3.22–3.19 (4H, m), 1.41 (6H, m); MS (ES⁺) 335.3 (M+1), (ES⁻) 333.3 (M-1), HPLC purity : 98.60%.

4-(Pirrolidino)-7-β-(D-ribofuranosyl)pyrrolo[3,2-d]pyrimidine (22d) :

¹H NMR (300 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆) : δ 12.45 (1H, s), 8.66 (1H, s), 8.01 (1H, s), 5.73–4.85 (3H, bs, D₂O exchangeable), 4.84–4.81 (1H, d, *J* 9.9 Hz), 4.45–4.40

(1H, m), 4.10–4.00 (1H, m), 3.76–3.74 (2H, d, *J* 10.2 Hz), 3.52–3.49 (1H, m), 3.40–3.38 (4H, m), 2.08–2.07 (4H, m); MS (ES⁺) 321.3 (M+1), (ES⁻) 319.3 (M-1), HPLC purity : 99.48%.

4-(Cyclopropylmethylamino)-7-β-(D-ribofuranosyl)-pyrrolo[3,2-d]pyrimidine (**22e**) :

¹H NMR (300 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆) : δ 11.80 (1H, s), 8.10 (1H, s), 7.74–7.70 (1H, t, *J* 1.5 Hz, D₂O exchangeable), 7.39 (1H, s), 5.22–5.09 (3H, bs, D₂O exchangeable), 4.36–4.33 (1H, d, *J* 9.9 and 10.5 Hz), 4.22–4.18 (1H, m), 3.94–3.91 (1H, m), 3.53–3.42 (4H, m), 3.23–3.19 (1H, d, *J* 5.7 Hz), 0.89–0.80 (1H, m), 0.24–0.18 (2H, m), 0.05–0.01 (2H, m); MS (ES⁺) 321.3 (M+1), (ES⁻) 319.3 (M-1), HPLC purity : 98.50%.

4-(Cyclopropylamino)-7-β-(D-ribofuranosyl)-pyrrolo[3,2-d]pyrimidine (**22f**) :

¹H NMR (300 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆) : δ 11.82 (1H, s), 8.18 (1H, s), 8.12–8.09 (1H, d, *J* 1.8 Hz, D₂O exchangeable), 7.45 (1H, s), 5.28–5.11 (3H, bs, D₂O exchangeable), 4.31–4.29 (1H, m), 4.19–4.15 (1H, m), 4.00–3.97 (1H, dd, *J* 9.9 and 10.5 Hz), 3.59–3.58 (2H, d, *J* 5.4 Hz), 3.21–3.20 (1H, m), 2.94–2.91 (1H, m), 0.78–0.72 (2H, m), 0.55–0.53 (2H, m); MS (ES⁺) 307.3 (M+1), (ES⁻) 305.3 (M-1), HPLC purity : 99.12%.

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